

Awareness and Adoption of Orange-Fleshed Sweet Potato (OFSP) as a Food Security Crop in Orlu Agricultural Zone, Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract: This study examined the awareness and adoption of Orange-Fleshed Sweet Potato (OFSP) among small holder farmers in the Orlu Agricultural Zone of Imo State, Nigeria. OFSP is biofortified with high levels of beta-carotene (a precursor to Vitamin A) and holds great potential to address food and nutritional insecurity, particularly vitamin A deficiency. A multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select 342 OFSP farmers from a population of 2,317. Data were collected using structured questionnaires, focus group discussions, and key informant interviews. Descriptive statistics and inferential tools, including the Tobit regression model and t-test, were used for data analysis. Results revealed that 78.3% of farmers were aware of OFSP, yet adoption was only 51.7%. key constraints included low consumer preference (75%), limited access to credit (70%), and high cost of inputs. The Tobit analysis identified education, farm size, extension contact, and perception of relative advantage as significant predictors of adoption. Findings underscore the need for intensified extension services and targeted policy interventions to promote OFSP as a sustainable food security strategy. The study fills a vital gap in literature regarding behavioral adoption patterns for OFSP among rural farmers in South-East Nigeria.

Keywords: *Orange-Fleshed Sweet Potato, Technology Adoption, Food Security, Vitamin A.*

Introduction

The growing challenge of food insecurity and malnutrition in Nigeria has necessitated

a focus on crops that combine productivity with nutritional value. One such crop is the Orange-Fleshed Sweet Potato (OFSP), a bio-fortified variety rich in beta-carotene.

According to the International Potato Center (CIP, 2017), Nigeria is the third largest producer of sweet potatoes globally. OFSP's adaptability, short maturity cycle, and nutritional benefits make it an ideal candidate for addressing micronutrient deficiencies-particularly Vitamin A deficiency, which is a major cause of childhood blindness and immune deficiency in Nigeria (Low et al., 2017; WHO, 2022).

The crop thrives in all of Nigeria's 36 states due to its broad agro-ecological adaptability and ability to grow in marginal soils CIP (2017). The production of Orange Fleshed Sweet Potato (OFSP) in Nigeria is a significant agricultural activity with both nutritional and economic importance. OFSP is a type of biofortified sweet potato that contains high levels of beta-carotene, which is converted to Vitamin A in the body after consumption. According to CIP (2017), this remarkable quality makes it a valuable crop in combating micronutrient malnutrition, particularly Vitamin A deficiency, which is a major public health problem in Nigeria. In terms of production yield, the OFSP variety has tremendously increased from about 3 tons to 20-30 tons per hectare. In some state in Nigeria, the total annual production of OFSP between 2014 to 2018 increased from 47,580 to 95,596 tones (Nwankwo et al, 2019). According to Babatunde et al (2019), the introduction and cultivation of OFSP are

promoted through various platforms and initiatives, aiming to enhance the nutritional intake among the population, especially in rural areas where access to food products rich in Vitamin A may be limited. These efforts also include increasing awareness and productivity among smallholder farmers, who are crucial in the cultivation and distribution of OFSP. Overall, the cultivation of OFSP in Nigeria is not only contributing to the fight against hidden hunger but also supporting smallholders in improving their livelihoods through increased income from higher productivity (Babatunde et al, 2019).

The food use of OFSP is varied with its various parts edible and useful for the human and animal consumption. According to Onunka, et al (2017), the leaves, roots and vines are edible and contains carbohydrate component. In addition, the fresh roots can be boiled, steamed, baked, and fried into chips and eaten, pounded or mixed with yam as porridge and or eaten with soup, roasted and eaten with oil or sauce and made into porridge (Ume et al., 2020). The roots can be processed into starch and use for industrial purpose and can be used in livestock feeding (Ume et al., 2020). In research conducted in Kenya, Owade et al (2018) reported that OFSP tubers have been utilized as food in their fresh form after cooking, as flour and in the grated and mashed (commonly known as puree) forms. OFSP flour has been used

locally at domestic level and in industrial production of bakery products. Some of the bakery products in which OFSP flour is incorporated as an ingredient are cakes, bread, muffins and buns. Mashed OFSP has also been used for flour substitution in Golden bread. OFSP is being promoted as a nutrition intervention to tackle VAD and food insecurity in many countries. In industrial production, OFSP has been used to produce products such as chips, Crisps, flour, puree, juice, bread and other bakery products.

Studies such as Owade et al. (2018) and Ume et al. (2020) have highlighted OFSP's utility in diverse food products ranging from flour and puree to baked goods. However, despite promotional efforts, the adoption rate among smallholder farmers remains suboptimal, particularly in southeastern Nigeria. Previous studies have focused more on production and value chains (Adebayo et al., 2019; Kabungo et al., 2019), with limited emphasis on adoption behavior. This study, therefore, aims to bridge this gap by examining the socioeconomic and institutional factors influencing awareness and adoption of OFSP in the Orlu Agricultural Zone of Imo State. General Objective of the study is to assess the level of awareness and adoption of Orange-Fleshed Sweet Potato (OFSP) as a food security crop among small holder farmers in Orlu Agricultural Zone, Imo State.

Methodology

Study Area

Imo a state in the Eastern part of Nigeria with its capital in Owerri was created in 1976 and is bordered to the north by Anambara State, Rivers State to the west and south, and Abia State to the east. The state economy is highly dependent on agricultural production, especially the production of palm oil, which a majority of citizens rely on for cooking. A key minor industry is the extraction of crude oil and natural gas, especially in Imo North and West. Imo State agricultural supervision under Agricultural Development Project (ADP) is divided into three agricultural Zones; Owerri, Orlu and Okigwe.

The study was conducted in Orlu agricultural zone of Imo State, Nigeria. The zone is located in tropical rainforest belt of Nigeria. The Orlu agricultural zone is made up of (10) Local Government Areas (LGAs). The LGAs in this zone include; Orlu, Njaba, Ideato South, Ideato North, Isu, Nwangele, Nkwere, Oru East, Oru West, and Orsu. The inhabitants of this zone are predominantly farmers, businessmen and civil servants. The common crops grown in the area are yam, cassava, oil palm, melon, potato and vegetables.

Research Design

A multistage sampling technique was used to select 342 farmers from a population of 2,317, calculated using Dillman's (2000) formula at 95% confidence level.

Data Collection

- a. Structured questionnaires
- b. Focus group discussions (FGD)
- c. Key informant Interviews (KII)

The population of the research is the small holder farmers who are involved in potato production in the agricultural zone. Multiple

stage sampling technique was used to select respondents. In the first stage, six (6) LGAs (Orsu, Ideato South, Orlu, Nkwere, Oru East and Njaba) out of the ten (10) were randomly selected, in the second stage, 8 villages were randomly selected from each of the six selected LGAs, making a total of 48 villages. From the headquarters of each LGA, the list of registered potato farmers was collected. The representative sample size of potato farmers in the LGAs was computed. The sample size was calculated from a finite population (2317) at a 95% confidence level and 5% of variability using the (Dillman, 2000) sampling model given by:

$$n = \frac{[(N \cdot P \cdot (1 - P))]}{\left[(N - 1) \cdot \left(\frac{B}{C}\right)^2 + P \cdot (1 - P) \right]} \text{----- (1)}$$

$$n = \frac{[(2317 \cdot 0.5 \cdot (1 - 0.5))]}{\left[(2317 - 1) \cdot \left(\frac{0.05}{1.96}\right)^2 + 0.5 \cdot (1 - 0.5) \right]} \text{----- (2)}$$

$$n = \frac{[579.25]}{[1.69]} = 342 \text{----- (3)}$$

Where n is the computed sample size needed for the desired level of precision; N is the population size; P is the proportion of population expected to choose; B is acceptable amount of sampling error, or precision; and finally, C is Z statistic associated with the confidence level which is 1.96 that corresponds to the 95% level. B can be set at 0.1, 0.05, or 0.03, which are ±

10, 5, or 3% of the true population value, respectively. The acceptable amount of sampling error or precision is set at 0.05 or 5%. Confidence level of 1.96 corresponds to the 95% level. Using 0.05 will lead to a greater sample size than using 0.03; however, it always provides an adequate sample size for a greater population (Biemer and Lyberg, 2003).

Table 1 Summary of Analytical Tools by Objective

Objective	Tool Used
1 – 3	Descriptive statistics
4	Tobit regression
5	Composite ranking

Results and Discussion

Table 2 Ages of the farmers

Age (Yrs.)	Data	
	(n= 342)	%
20 – 29	27	8
30 – 39	60	17
40 – 49	130	38
50 – 59	90	26
60 – 69	13	4
>69	22	7
Mean Age	45	16.7

Table 3 Educational levels of the farmers

Levels	Data	
	(n=342)	%
Non Formal Education	0	0
Primary	135	39
Secondary	165	49
Tertiary	42	12

Table 4a Marital status of the farmers by gender

Status	Data	
	(n = 342)	%
Single	113	33
Married	229	67

Table 4b Household size of the farmers

Size (Number)	Data	
	(n = 342)	%
1 – 5	182	53
6 – 10	100	29
11 – 15	60	18

Table 5 Land ownership structure of the farmers

Structures	Data	
	n = 342	%
Inherited	193	56
Purchased	89	26
Rented	40	12
Gift	20	6

Table 6 Distribution of farmers according to Farm Size

Size (Hectare)	Data	
	n = 342	%
1.0 – 1.99	84	25
2.0 – 2.99	178	52
>2.99	80	23

Table 7 Potato Farming Experience of Farmers

Experience (Yrs)	Data	
	(n = 342)	%
1 – 5	88	26
6 – 10	142	42
11 – 15	70	20
>15	42	12

Table 8 Level of income of the farmers

Levels (₦)	Data	
	n = 342	%
100, 000 – 290, 000	5	3
300, 000 – 490, 000	67	43
500, 000 – 690, 000	46	30
>690, 000	37	24

Table 9 Frequency of extension contact of the farmers

Frequency of Contact	Data	
	(n=342)	%
No Contact	70	20
Once a Week	45	13
Once a Month	90	26
Once in two Months	73	21
Quarterly	64	19

Table 10 Distribution of farmer's sources of information on Orange Fresh Potato in the Study Area

Variables	Data		
	(n = 342)	%	Rank
Extension Contact	298	87	1 st
Farmers' groups	251	73	2 nd
Friends/Relatives and neighbours	210	61	3 rd
Local Market	182	53	4 th
Agricultural programme on Radio	134	39	5 th
Agricultural programme on Television	98	29	6 th
Print Media (Bulletin, Newspaper, Hand Bills, Manuals)	67	20	7 th
Internet	55	16	8 ^h

* = Multiple responses

Table 11 Percentage distribution of farmers' perception of the information from the sources

Sources of Information	Data (n = 342)*					
	Available	Credible	Reliable	Comprehensive	Useful	CPS
Extension Contact	75	90	88	75	80	82
Farmers' Group	80	84	85	68	70	77
Radio	78	77	80	70	73	75
Television	70	71	76	68	70	71
Local Market	75	54	50	55	47	56
Friends/Relatives and neighbours	60	43	39	31	29	40
Print Media	32	40	55	25	20	34
Internet	18	20	25	22	28	23

* Multiple response; CPS = Composite Perception Score

Table 12 Distribution of farmers' extents of adoption of OFSP and Local White Potato varieties production Practices

Adoption Practices for Potato	OFSP		LWP	
	f*	%	f*	%
Use certified disease-free potatoes seed	251	73	321	94
Cut larger seed potatoes into pieces, each with at least one "eye" or bud	225	66	310	90
Preparation of ridge or hills	188	55	278	81
Planting in well-drained loamy soils	165	48	261	76
Planting space of 30 cm apart in rows that are 75 cm apart and 10-15 cm deep	143	42	231	68
Apply nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium (N-P-K at the ratio of 6-3-9) Fertilizers	121	35	213	62
Use mulching and herbicides (either Metribuzin, Pendimethalin, Glyphosate, Rimsulfuron, Linuron or Ethalfluralin) to manage weeds	104	30	174	51
Use neonicotinoids, pyrethroids, chlorothalonil, mancozeb, Oxamyl for pest and disease control	76	22	152	44
Use of irrigation but avoid water-log	68	19	126	37
Harvest within 90-120 days after planting when the vines die	57	16	96	28
Store potatoes in a cool, dark, and well-ventilated area and avoid exposure to light	52	15	84	25
Average Percentage		38.27		59.63

Table 13 Tobit Regressions of Socioeconomic and Technological Factors Influencing Adoption of Orange Fleshed Sweet Potato

Variables	Data		
	B	SE	t-ratio
(Constant)	.2419	.0720	3.3597
Age	-.0116	.0063	-1.8412
Education	.0813	.0335	2.4268**
Marital Status	.0661	.0223	2.9641***
Farm Size	.0812	.0323	2.5139***
Household Size	.0068	.0030	2.2666**
Land Ownership Structure	.0451	.0311	1.5401
Farming Experience	.0912	.0629	1.4499
Level of Income	.0026	.0009	2.8888***
Extension Contact	.0072	.0029	2.4827**
Relative Advantage	.0020	.0008	2.5000***
Compatibility	.0801	.0614	1.3045
Affordability	.0069	.0042	1.6428
Complexity	-.0416	.0322	-1.2929
Sigma	.4413	.0929	4.7502
Log Likelihood Function	-84.7621		

** = Sig @ 5%; *** = Sig @ 1%

Table 14 Problems farmers encountered in adopting Orange Fleshed Sweet Potato

Constraining Factors	Data (n = 342)		
	n*	%	Rank
High cost of labour	286	83	1 st
Inadequate credit facility	241	70	2 nd
High cost of material inputs	220	64	3 rd
Inadequate access to Land	208	60	4 th
High cost of the seedlings	176	51	5 th
Pest and disease	152	44	6 th
Inadequate availability of ready market	121	35	7 th
Poor road network	98	28	8 th
Complexity of the technology involved	62	18	9 th
Culture and tradition of the people	48	14	10 th

Table 15 Differences in the adoption of OFSP and LWP

Potato Varieties	Mean	Standard Deviation	t- value	p-value
OFSP	3.283	1.689		
			2.53	0.035*
LWP	3.421	1.958		

* = Significant at 5%. Critical t-value = 1.963. (Source: Field Survey Data, 2024.)

The socio-demographic profile of the farmers indicates that the majority were in their active and productive age group (mean = 45 years), with most falling between 40–59 years (64%). This suggests that potato farming in the area is dominated by middle-aged individuals who are physically active and have accumulated experience, making them more receptive to new technologies (Manda et al., 2020). The educational profile shows that nearly all respondents had at least a primary (39%) or secondary education (49%), which enhances the ability to access, interpret, and apply agricultural information. Education has consistently

been identified as a strong determinant of agricultural innovation adoption (Adekoya et al., 2021). The high proportion of married farmers (67%) also indicates greater household labor availability and stability in farming decisions.

Household size was relatively large, with 47% of households having more than six members, which may provide family labor. In terms of land tenure, more than half (56%) inherited their farmland, which reflects traditional land acquisition patterns in Nigeria. Secure land tenure encourages long-term investment in improved practices

(Place et al., 2018). The majority of farmers (52%) cultivated 2.0–2.99 hectares, suggesting semi-commercial scale potato production. Farming experience was substantial, with 42% having 6–10 years of potato farming experience, which can improve efficiency and willingness to adopt innovations (Tambo & Wünscher, 2017). Income distribution revealed that most farmers earned ₦300,000–490,000 annually (43%), suggesting moderate financial capacity, which could limit adoption of input-intensive technologies. Economic capacity is a critical determinant of adoption of improved crop varieties, especially when labor and input costs are high (Asfaw et al., 2012).

Extension contact was relatively weak, with 20% of farmers reporting no contact and only 13% having weekly visits. Yet, extension (87%) and farmers' groups (73%) ranked as the most important sources of information on OFSP. This aligns with findings that extension services and farmer-to-farmer networks are crucial for promoting biofortified crops in Nigeria (Ilona et al., 2017). In terms of credibility, extension services scored highest (CPS = 82), followed by farmers' groups (77) and radio (75). This reflects trust in formal agricultural advisory systems compared with informal sources (Munyua et al., 2019). When comparing adoption practices,

farmers had much higher adoption of LWP practices (average = 59.63%) compared to OFSP (38.27%). For example, 94% of farmers used certified seeds for LWP versus 73% for OFSP, and the use of recommended fertilizer rates, pest control, and irrigation was significantly lower for OFSP. This disparity reflects farmers' greater familiarity with LWP, coupled with market certainty and reduced risk perception (Chiona et al., 2019). Adoption stages further confirm this: 61% fully adopted LWP, while only 39% adopted OFSP, with many still at awareness (20%) and trial (15%) stages. This slow uptake is consistent with the diffusion of innovations theory, which suggests that unfamiliarity and perceived risk hinder adoption of new varieties (Rogers, 2003).

The Tobit regression showed that education, marital status, farm size, household size, income level, extension contact, and perceived relative advantage significantly influenced OFSP adoption. Similar findings have been reported in studies on adoption of biofortified and improved crop varieties in sub-Saharan Africa (Oparinde et al., 2016; Manda et al., 2020). Conversely, age had a negative effect, indicating that younger farmers are more open to innovation, consistent with previous adoption studies (Adekoya et al., 2021). Constraints to adoption were also evident, with high labor cost (83%), inadequate credit (70%), high

input costs (64%), and limited land (60%) ranking highest. These findings mirror constraints identified in studies on OFSP and other biofortified crops in Nigeria, where financial and institutional bottlenecks limit uptake despite nutritional benefits (Ilona et al., 2017; Low et al., 2017). Finally, the t-test showed a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.035$) between adoption of OFSP and LWP, confirming that the traditional white variety is more widely adopted due to familiarity, established markets, and lower perceived risks compared to the relatively new OFSP. This suggests that strengthening OFSP promotion requires addressing both economic barriers and trust in the technology.

Conclusion

This study identifies significant awareness of OFSP among smallholder farmers in the Orlu Agricultural Zone, but moderate adoption levels due to economic and structural barriers. The research fills an important gap in understanding behavioural and institutional constraints to biofortified crop adoption in Nigeria. By highlighting key socioeconomic and technological drivers of adoption, the study contributes new insights to policy and extension program design aimed at achieving food and nutritional security in rural communities. It is therefore important

to strengthen extension services and farmer education programs on OFSP benefits. Facilitate access to credit and subsidized inputs to reduce cost constraints. Develop consumer awareness campaigns to increase demand and preference for OFSP and promote OFSP product development to enhance marketability.

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References

- Adebayo, O. O., et al. (2019). OFSP and rural nutrition in Nigeria. *Journal of Food security. African Journal of Food and Nutrition*, 4(2), 101-115.
- Adekoya, A. J., Ojo, T. O., & Ologeh, I. O. (2021). Socio-economic determinants of adoption of improved agricultural technologies among smallholder farmers in Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*, 25(2), 77–87. <https://doi.org/10.4314/jae.v25i2.8>
- Asfaw, S., Shiferaw, B., Simtowe, F., & Lipper, L. (2012). Impact of modern agricultural technologies on smallholder welfare: Evidence

- from Tanzania and Ethiopia. *Food Policy*, 37(3), 283–295.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2012.02.013>
- Babatunde, R. O., et al. (2019). OFSP adoption and income among smallholders.
- Bouis, H. E., & Saltzman, A. (2017). Improving nutrition through biofortification: A review of evidence from HarvestPlus. *Global Food Security*, 12, 49-58.
- Chiona, S., Kalinda, T. H., & Tembo, G. (2019). Adoption of improved maize seed varieties in Southern Zambia. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 35(4), 1–13.
<https://doi.org/10.9734/ajaees/2019/v35i430211>
- Egwuonwu, H.O., et al. (2024). OFSP as climate-resilient crop in Southeastern Nigeria. *African Journal of Food and Nutrition*.
- Ekenta, C.M., et al. (2023). Socioeconomic drivers of OFSP adoption. *Journal of Agricultural Extension*.
- Ezeano, C.I., & Nnadozie, C. I. (2022). Factors influencing adoption of OFSP in Nigeria. *Journal of Extension Systems*, 38(1), 23-30.
- Ilona, P., Bouis, H. E., Palenberg, M., Moursi, M., & Oparinde, A. (2017). Vitamin A maize in Nigeria: Crop development and delivery. *African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development*, 17(2), 11893–11904.
<https://doi.org/10.18697/ajfand.78>
[HarvestPlus13](https://www.harvestplus.org/)
- Low, J. W., et al. (2017). Sweet potato and food security in sub-Saharan Africa.
- Low, J. W., Mwangi, R. O. M., Andrade, M., Carey, E., & Ball, A. M. (2017). Tackling vitamin A deficiency with biofortified sweetpotato in sub-Saharan Africa. *Global Food Security*, 14, 23–30.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2017.01.004>
- Manda, J., Khonje, M. G., Alene, A. D., Tufa, A. H., Abdoulaye, T., Mutenje, M., & Manyong, V. (2020). Does cooperative membership increase and accelerate agricultural technology adoption? Empirical evidence from Zambia. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*,

- 158, 120160.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2020.120160>
- Munyua, H., Adera, E., & Jensen, M. (2019). Emerging ICTs and their potential in revitalizing small-scale agriculture in Africa. *Agricultural Information Worldwide*, 5(1), 3–9.
- Njoku, M.E., Chukwu, M. A., & Uche, I.A. (2020). Awareness and adoption of OFSP in South-East Nigeria. *Nigerian Agricultural Journal*, 51(2), 88-95.
- Nwakor, N.N., et al. (2021). Gender and adoption of OFSP. *Journal of Gender Studies in Agriculture*, 3(1), 40-50.
- Okello, J.J., et al. (2019). Adoption pathways of biofortified crops in Nigeria. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 14(9), 532-540.
- Oparinde, A., Banerji, A., Birol, E., & Ilona, P. (2016). Information and consumer willingness to pay for biofortified yellow cassava: Evidence from experimental auctions in Nigeria. *Agricultural Economics*, 47(2), 215–233.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/agec.12223>
- Owade, J.O., et al. (2018). Utilization of OFSP in Kenya. *International Journal of Agricultural Innovations*.
- Place, F., Meybeck, A., & Holloway, G. (2018). Land tenure security and sustainable development. *FAO Land and Water Discussion Paper 15*. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization.
- Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of innovations* (5th ed.). Free Press.
- Tambo, J. A., & Wünscher, T. (2017). Adoption and adaptation of natural resource management innovations in smallholder agriculture: Reflections on key lessons and best practices. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 19(5), 1209–1228.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-016-9791-6>
- Ume, S.I., et al. (2020). Utilization and perception of OFSP in Imo State. *Nigerian Agricultural Journal*.
- WHO (2022). Vitamin A Deficiency and Global Health Risks. Geneva: WHO Publications.